

Field Data (fictional)

Site Biscoff Bay	Date 2011-02-12	
Station G1	Station Surface temp (°C) 20.1	Transect length (m) 30 m

Transect	Quadrat	Lat start	Lon start	Lat end	Lon end	Mid-point lon	Mid-point lat	Depth min	Depth max	Zostera % cover	Aurelia aurita	Clupea harengus (adult)	Clupea harengus (juvenile)
1	1	54.501	18.559	54.501	18.572	18.5662	54.5005	0.8	4	30			
1	2	54.501	18.559	54.501	18.572	18.5662	54.5005	0.8	4	60			
1	3	54.501	18.559	54.501	18.572	18.5662	54.5005	0.8	4	85			
1		54.501	18.559	54.501	18.572	18.5662	54.5005	0.8	4		10	23	3
2		54.4856	18.5696	54.4859	18.5835	18.5766	54.4857	0.5	6		3	14	9

Darwin Core Term Definitions

DwC term	Class	Definition
eventID	Event	A unique identifier for an event that happened at a specific time and place, such as a sample collection or observation. Can be constructed e.g. DATE_Site_Station_Transect_Quadrat
eventDate	Event	The date or time when the event occurred. For example, the day a sample was collected or an observation was made.
eventType	Event	What kind of event occurred. Recommended to use controlled vocabulary: Site visit, Transect, Sample...
maximumDepthInMetres minimumDepthInMetres	Location	The deepest and shallowest points where the event or observation occurred, measured in meters.
locality	Location	The name/description of where the event happened, e.g. specific location or area. Broader location details (like country or ocean) can be listed elsewhere.
decimalLongitude and decimalLatitude	Location	The exact geographical coordinates (latitude and longitude) of where the event happened, in decimal degrees.
footprintWKT	Location	Description of the shape or area where the event took place, e.g. line, point, polygon, or collection of multiple shapes. Must be in Well-Known Text format. E.g. LINestring(LON LAT, LON LAT, LON LAT)
occurrenceID	Occurrence	A unique identifier for the specific observation of an organism, ensuring it is distinguishable from other occurrences. Even if the same species is observed, if the observations occur at two different places & times, a unique identifier is needed for both. Can be constructed e.g. DATE_Site_Station_Transect_Quadrat_Species1

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scientificName	Taxon	The full scientific name of the species, including the author's name and year, if known
occurrenceStatus	Occurrence	Whether the species was present or absent during the event. Must be either “present” or “absent”
basisOfRecord	Occurrence	The type of observation, select from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HumanObservation • MachineObservation • MaterialEntity • PreservedSpecimen • FossilSpecimen • LivingSpecimen • MaterialSample • (more on the online DWC term list)
lifestage	Occurrence	The age or life stage of the organism at the time it was recorded. Recommended to use controlled vocabulary
organismQuantity	Occurrence	The number of organisms observed or measured. Recommended to also include this information in eMoF to include controlled vocabulary
organismQuantityType	Occurrence	The unit used to count or measure organisms, such as "individuals" or "percent cover", “abundance”. Recommended to also include this information in eMoF to include associated controlled vocabulary
measurementType	Measurement	Describes what was measured, e.g. temperature, biomass, name of a sampling device, organism quantity, etc.
measurementValue	Measurement	The actual value of the measurement
measurementUnit	Measurement	The units for the measurement, e.g. "degrees Celsius". May be left blank for unitless measurements (like the name of a sampling device)